

Unlock Value from Agroforestry Wood: The Role of Scrimber and Laminated Strand Lumber

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Wood as a Key Renewable Material in a Circular Bioeconomy

Wood has always been one of humanity's most versatile renewable materials. In the context of a modern bioeconomy, its potential applications appear almost limitless. The bioeconomy aims to produce, develop, and utilize biological resources, processes, and systems to provide products, processes, and services across all sectors of a sustainable economic system (BMBF & BMEL, 2020). Within this framework, wood is among the most important renewable raw materials on the path to a bio-based future (FNR, 2024).

Wood stores carbon during growth and releases oxygen through photosynthesis, making its use both climate-friendly and resource-efficient. The material utilization of wood - before its eventual energetic use - extends its carbon storage period, thereby directly supporting climate protection goals and the objectives of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy (EU Commission, 2025).

Agroforestry systems, where trees and crops or livestock coexist on the same piece of land, deliver multiple ecosystem services (Kähkönen & den Herder, 2025) – among others carbon sequestration in the form of wood. Due to its quality and structure, wood from fast-growing trees produced in short or medium rotations is generally not suitable for direct construction. However, it is suitable for innovative technical products such as scrimber and laminated strand lumber (Figure 1) – both high-performance materials that are suitable for all construction applications.

FIGURE 1. Schematic production process for scrimber (left) and laminated strand lumber (right) – (AI generated)

From Agroforestry to High-Value Wood Products

One promising approach within European agroforestry is to broaden the range of wood valorization pathways, combining both material and energetic uses. While the production of firewood or wood chips for renewable energy remains an important and established practice, expanding material applications - from veneer and furniture wood to innovative engineered products - offers additional opportunities for value creation and long-term carbon storage.

A high-value product pathway can originate from alley cropping (Fischer et al., 2025a), in which rows of trees are integrated between agricultural crops or pastures. Over decades, these trees can produce high-quality veneer logs. Success depends on careful species selection and appropriate management to achieve straight, knot-free stems with sufficient diameter and volume (Fischer et al., 2025b). However, this process requires long rotation periods of 50 to 70 years, which makes returns uncertain due to price volatility and market risks.

As an alternative to these long-term cycles, agroforestry can employ fast-growing species (see also Fischer & Zander, 2025) such as hybrid poplars or willows with medium rotation lengths (Figure 2). These provide feedstock not only for energy use but

increasingly for innovative wood-based materials like Scrimber and Laminated Strand Lumber (LSL) products that offer new opportunities for earlier value creation.

FIGURE 2. Woody biomass from fast-growing tree species such as poplar (left) and willow (right) can be used not only for energy production but also as a renewable resource for material applications through innovative processing technologies. (photo: Fischer / ZALF)

Scrimber: Engineered Strength from Raw Wood Fibres

Scrimber is an innovative composite wood product that is produced by crushing whole logs and branches into long fiber strands, which are then dried and impregnated with resin (Scrimber CSC AG, n.d.). The partially dried strands are aligned and pressed under heat to form solid structural profiles.

The resulting scrimber beams have mechanical properties suitable for heavy-duty construction posts and beams, but can be produced from lower-quality logs and various tree species, including those from agroforestry systems. The production process is currently in development. A pilot plant is able to process small branches as well as logs up to 40 cm diameter. A key advantage of scrimber technology is its ability to utilize low-quality roundwood, including thin, short, curved, or otherwise irregular logs, as well as a wide range of tree species, highlighting the flexibility of the technology with respect to feedstock geometry and quality. This makes scrimber particularly well suited for biomass originating from agroforestry systems. According to Scrimber CSC AG, material yields of up to approximately 90% can be achieved from the input log, significantly exceeding those of conventional sawn timber products.

Laminated Strand Lumber (LSL): Efficient Use of Small-Diameter Trees

Laminated Strand Lumber (LSL) is an engineered wood product made from oriented strands bonded under heat and pressure (Hasan et al., 2023). Unlike Scrimber, LSL strands are produced by flaking rather than crushing the logs, resulting in more uniform, consistent strands. This method, however, requires logs of standardized length and quality to ensure the production of uniform strands. Panels can reach thicknesses of up to 90 mm and are suitable for beams, panels, and structural elements in construction.

Crucially, LSL utilizes smaller-diameter and lower-quality logs compared to conventional wood construction products, which perfectly fits the resource base of European agroforestry systems with fast-growing species such as poplar, willow, or alder.

Key advantages of LSL include:

- Consistent strength, dimensional stability, and durability.
- Adaptability to different hardwood or softwood species.
- Lower production costs compared to solid structural timber.
- Suitability for various sectors such as construction, furniture, and packaging.

By tailoring production parameters, LSL can be optimized for specific applications. Research shows that LSL made from mixed hardwood species performs remarkably well (Hasan et al., 2023), meeting both mechanical and environmental standards while supporting low-carbon construction.

Both Scrimber and Laminated Strand Lumber (LSL) enable farmers to channel local wood resources into regional material markets. A key advantage of these engineered wood products is their suitability for logs that are otherwise considered low quality, including irregular shapes and smaller sizes that are unsuitable for conventional wood construction products such as cross-laminated timber (CLT). For farmers producing small-diameter or irregularly shaped trees, the production of Scrimber and LSL offers an attractive value-added opportunity, bridging the gap between low-grade biomass and high-performance building materials. However, the fabrication of these engineered wood products requires advanced processing plants for resin impregnation, controlled drying of the strands, and high-pressure pressing, which limits the potential for fully decentralized or on-site production. As a result, transport and storage of the raw biomass must be carefully planned to ensure efficiency and cost-effectiveness.

In addition to Scrimber and LSL, other wood-based panels can be manufactured from low-grade yet fast-growing biomass. Oriented strand boards (OSB) produced from fast-growing hardwood species such as poplar, willow, and birch have been shown to exhibit improved mechanical properties and slightly reduced thickness swelling compared to OSB made from mixed softwood species (Lunguleasa et al., 2020). Beyond wood-based feedstocks, particleboard can be manufactured from a wide range of agricultural biomass, including straw, crop stalks and leaves. Lee et al. (2022) demonstrated that particleboards produced from such alternative raw materials often achieve mechanical properties comparable to, or even exceeding, those of conventional wood-based particleboards.

New Value Chains and Agroforestry Business Models

Traditional agroforestry value chains have primarily focused on energy wood and long-term high-quality timber. However, innovative materials like Scrimber and LSL introduce intermediate value streams that can shorten rotation periods and diversify farm income.

Their advantages include:

- Earlier returns from agroforestry plantations compared to high-value timber.
- Efficient use of all tree components, minimizing waste.
- Flexibility in species use, encouraging biodiversity and resilience.
- Regional bioeconomy development through distributed production networks.
- Reduction of over-exploitation of softwoods needed in the construction sector.

Economically, producing engineered wood materials can stimulate local cooperatives and Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) focused on processing and added-value generation. Strategically, these approaches align with EU Green Deal objectives, promoting sustainable rural development, resource efficiency, and carbon neutrality by 2050 (EU Commission, 2019).

The evolution of agroforestry wood utilization through technologies such as Scrimber and LSL serves as a bridge to modern bio-based industry. These innovations complement — not replace — conventional sustainable forestry by creating economic opportunities for farmers, reducing pressure on natural forests, and increasing material output through higher land equivalent ratios and productivity through agroforestry systems.

Highlights:

- Scrimber and Laminated Strand Lumber enable efficient medium-rotation use of agroforestry wood
- The innovative production processes result in high-quality construction material
- These technologies advance climate goals, resilience, and local economic growth
- Adoption drives a future circular bioeconomy aligned with European objectives

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